

TOPIC: HELIANTHUS TUBEROSUS AND ITS IMPORTANCE

Ismailov Sh.F.¹, Madrahimov Sh.N.²

^{1,2}Tashkent pharmaceutical institute

Email: shohrux.farruxovich98@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6467070>

Relevance of the topic. It is known that biotechnological from natural sources polysaccharides using the methods and nutrients needed for the national economy obtaining is one of the current challenges facing food biotechnology. In this regard, especially the artichoke plant grown in our region is quite promising. Different for different foods from this plant saccharides and minerals can be obtained. As well as the plant Consumption of the nodule in various ways is positive for human health It is no secret that Difficulties in creating conditions for synthetic synthesis processes as a result of obtaining various biologically active substances and polymers for food and medical purposes from plants that are natural sources, and the methods of its separation and purification lead to an increase in product cost, how to synthesize synthetic products It should be noted that there is a lack of information about the secret and the widespread use of plant sources, and the substances derived from them have a natural character. Helianthus tuberosus plant and producers involved in the fermentation process, the subject is a set of biotechnological methods and technologies. Helianthus tuberosus Asteraceae belongs to the family and is a perennial herbaceous plant. Height 1.5-2 meter plant. The stems are leafy, hairy, facing upwards branched. The leaves are large, stout, elongated, the leaf blade ovate, The edges are trimmed, the stem is opposite. The flowers are collected in a basket and placed individually. Shopping Cart in the middle is fake tongue-shaped flowers at the edges of the tube. Of flowers, The color is bright orange. This plant does not produce seeds. July-August blooms in Geographical distribution. Homeland is mainly North America. At the moment Helianthus tuberosus America, France, England, Norway, Sweden, Russia, It is grown in large areas in Ukraine and Central Asia. The appearance of the product. At the ends of the underground stems, the shape of the fruit is noxious. The main fruit is formed in the center of the root, their shape resembles a variety of potatoes. The specific smell of the product has a taste to be used. Helianthus tuberosus plant improves gastric and intestinal function activates, occurs in it, pathogenic bacteria, viruses and increases resistance to pests. Tuberculosis, osteochondrosis, in the prevention of kidney disease, influenza, angina, oncological diseases and is the most effective plant in treatment. Helianthus tuberosus is mainly used as a food plant for livestock. In medicine, the inulin substance at its end is used. It is a cold-resistant, short-day plant in the northern regions that can also be grown. Its surface is also resistant to frosts of 6 degrees can give. When the end is frozen, it can thaw again. Helianthus tuberosus is the most common of all cultivated plants in Uzbekistan the soil is flexible in climatic conditions (except saline soils). 25-50 gram tubers of ground pear are planted. If it is cut and planted productivity can be reduced by 25–30 percent. If the end is too large (70-80 g), it is better to cut it before planting. Cut ends it is recommended to sow only in the spring. Planted in the fall it will not be possible to harvest. 50-60 thousand per hectare or 0.6-2.0 tons of seeds are sown. February in two terms depending on climatic conditions in which artichokes are grown sown in late March-early March and late October-early November. Planting depth depends on the size of the planted

end, it is 5-12 cm planted in a scheme of 70 x 35 x 40 cm in depth. After planting, the seedlings sprout the land is rained once or twice. Since the seedlings have fully sprouted then the seedling spacing is cultivated after each watering. If a stranger if the grass has multiplied, the row spacing is cut. Helianthus tuberosus soil requires more of the nutrients it contains. A ton of harvest removes 3 kg of nitrogen, 1.5 kg of phosphorus and 4.5 kg of potassium from the soil In Uzbekistan, silage is harvested in late October and in late November harvested with combine harvesters. Harvesting the finished crop in winter lasts until the season. Helianthus tuberosus is affected by white rot disease may beetle and turnip canals infect it.

Literature:

1. Ч. Алтанчимэг, Д. Цэнджав, Х. Даариймаа and С. Сээсрэгдорж, "Өндөр зоосон цэцэг (Inula helenium L.), Эмийн бамбайн (Valeriana officinalis L.) Монгол улсын үндэсний фармакопейн өгүүлэл боловсруулсан судалгаа," Монголын уламжлалт анагаах ухаан, pp. 67-70, 2012.
2. A. Dominguez, L. Rodrigues, N. Lima and J. Teixeira, "An overview of the recent developments on fructooligosaccharide production and applications," Food Bioprocess Technol, vol. 7, p. 324–337, 2014.
3. I. Panchev, N. Delchev, D. Kovacheva and A. Slavov, "Physicochemical characteristics of inulins obtained from Jerusalem artichoke (Helianthus tuberosus L.)," Eur. Food Res. Technol, vol. 233, p. 889–896, 2011.